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FEEDBACK LITERACY AS A PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE FOR FIRST-YEAR ENGINEERING STUDENTS: STUDENTS' FEEDBACK EXPERIENCES

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ABSTRACT

Feedback has a major influence on learning and achievement, but students are not always aware of opportunities and responsibilities that come with it. To benefit the most from feedback opportunities, it is important for students to perceive feedback as useful, while feeling accountable and self-assured to be able to take action. In this paper a focus group discussion is conducted with first-year engineering students to understand how students experience feedback processes and what their beliefs about feedback are. Students see continuous feedback as an important goal of feedback processes, but underestimate the importance of their own active role in the process. They clearly prefer oral and individual feedback to have an opportunity to start a dialogue, but are reluctant to do so in an online setting or through email. The final goal

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is to introduce feedback literacy as a professional competence, so students become aware of their role as active learners in the feedback process.

1 INTRODUCTION

Feedback is among the most critical influences on learning and achievement [1]. There is a growing acknowledgment that feedback needs to be a learning-centred process where students' ability to actively engage with and utilise feedback processes needs more attention [2], [3]. Since students predominantly hold a teacher-driven view of 'feedback as telling' in which feedback is often limited to an input [2], it is important for learners to develop student feedback literacy as a key mechanism for maximising the potential of feedback processes [2]–[4]. Carless and Boud [5, p. 1316] define feedback literacy as "the understandings, capacities and dispositions needed to make sense of information and use it to enhance work or learning strategies". Activities such as reflecting on a wide range of assessment experiences, have the potential to nurture self-regulatory learning behaviours, making it possible for feedback literate students to improve performance or learning strategies [6], [7]. Since feedback literacy is also a valuable professional asset, it can be seen as a steppingstone towards a lifelong learning mindset [5]. Molloy et al. [2] state that the development of feedback literacy should be an embedded strategy as part of existing activities and should be introduced early in the first year. This way students can benefit the most from the curriculum and are not dependent on the limited opportunities for input from educators [2].

This paper focusses on the results of a focus group discussion with first-year engineering students in order to understand how they experience feedback processes and to gain insight into their beliefs about feedback. The focus group discussion is analysed based on the feedback literacy framework of Carless and Boud [5].

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Participants

All 88 first-year engineering students of the Faculty of Engineering Technology (KU Leuven, Campus De Nayer) were asked to voluntarily participate in a focus group discussion. A limited number of only 4 students participated, all male (total cohort 84% male, 16% female).

2.2 Focus Group Discussion

The focus group discussion was organised at the beginning of the second semester of the academic year 2020-2021, and was conducted in an online setting, lasting 1.5 hours. It started with rapport-building through mutual introductions to maximize interaction between participants. The semi-structured format was based on Kitzinger [8]. The facilitator's involvement was minimized to asking introductory questions and keeping the discussion focused. The discussed topics were related to the meaning of feedback, earlier feedback experiences, and expectations and barriers regarding dealing with feedback.

The focus group discussion was transcribed verbatim and thematically analysed. The transcript was first read in depth while writing down initial codes. Themes were then constructed based on the feedback literacy definition of Carless and Boud [5].

Ethical approval was obtained for this study from our university's Ethics Committee (G-2020-2354) and participants have consented to be part of this research. They were informed that their participation was voluntary and that the analysis would be conducted anonymously.

3 RESULTS

The feedback literacy framework of Carless and Boud [5] consists of inter-related features with the goal of maximizing potential for students to take action and engage with feedback, being (1) the appreciation of their own active role in the feedback process, (2) the continuous development of capacities for making judgments about their own work and the work of others, and (3) managing affect in positive ways. The findings of the focus group discussion are grouped according to the relevant themes.

3.1 Appreciating feedback

3.1.1 *“Feedback literate students understand and appreciate the role of feedback in improving work and the active learner role in these processes.”*

All students agree that one of the purposes of feedback is continuous improvement: feedback makes it possible to perform on a higher level for a subsequent task than the level that is possible without getting feedback. They see feedback as an input for adjusting their performance towards the required standards, but also mention this as a barrier since the exact requirements are not always clear.

3.1.2 *“Feedback literate students recognise that feedback information comes in different forms and from different sources.”*

One student states that feedback is very wide and consists of all possible kinds of information, even facial expressions during a conversation. He also mentions scoring on a test: a low grade signals him “to study harder” or to question how a teacher might have wanted it differently.

During the discussion, all students agree that feedback comes in formative and summative form. When they think of feedback examples, they initially refer to formative comments on presentation and writing skills, based on their earlier experiences. One student clearly approaches summative feedback on a test as a linear relationship to “how much he knows” about a specific topic and finds this the best possible feedback. It enables him to reflect if he made up to the expectations or not. Later in the discussion, all students prefer formative feedback because it is more detailed and thus provides a better opportunity to improve.

Most students appreciate group feedback after an exam, but favour individual feedback. Their preference goes towards oral feedback because it offers the opportunity to start a dialogue and ask for specific details in order to fully understand the message. A video call can be a valuable option, but a face to face dialogue is preferred because that way it is easier to go through a document, such as a report or

an exam, together. All students agree that a chat session cannot replace an oral discussion as the message can be open to interpretation.

One student explicitly mentions that he mainly seeks feedback from people that can help him best, such as a teacher, but also specific friends or classmates.

3.1.3 “Feedback literate students use technology to access, store and revisit feedback.”

One student refers to task submission forms which he used in the past. These forms had a feedback field and made it possible to access collected feedback at a later stage. None of the students took any further initiative to use technology of their own to store collected feedback. They write things down on a piece of paper or in a course textbook itself to find it back automatically when reaching out to the core information. One student explicitly states he remembers feedback and does not write it down, even after another student indicates only remembering such information is dangerous because you might lose the exact message over time.

3.2 Making judgments

3.2.1 “Feedback literate students develop capacities to make sound academic judgments about their own work and the work of others.”

One student suggested ‘a moment of reflection’ as a synonym for feedback, because it improves judging his own work. Another student mentions he “can do feedback on his own” if he has “input data” such as the correct solutions on exam questions or exercises. The group agrees this can be true for an exam, but not for an open exercise because it is too difficult to judge all the individual subtopics. For an open exercise they conclude formative feedback is essential.

3.2.2 “Feedback literate students participate productively in peer feedback processes.”

All students agree that having regular meetings during a teamwork is a valuable form of giving feedback to each other. If they do not work together as a team and receive feedback from individual classmates, they clearly state they hardly take it into account because they do not rely on the competence of their peers and see the teacher feedback as the only valid input.

3.2.3 “Feedback literate students refine self-evaluative capacities over time in order to make more robust judgments.”

The students did not explicitly mention self-evaluative aspects during the focus group discussion, but one student mentioned dealing with feedback as a permanent weighing of accepting or rejecting the feedback information. He will always listen to feedback, but only if he is convinced it will improve his performance and fits his way of working, he takes the feedback advice into account. A second student confirms, but questions if it is a real choice or something that happens “automatically” without actively questioning the feedback information. A third student simply mentions he only listens to feedback if he is not satisfied with his results. If he’s convinced for himself he did a good job, he won’t listen to feedback, even if he received a near-pass grade.

3.3 Managing affect

3.3.1 *“Feedback literate students maintain emotional equilibrium and avoid defensiveness when receiving critical feedback.”*

One student argues that criticism or “negative feedback” cannot be seen as valuable feedback if it does not contain opportunities to improve. A second student steps in and confirms the statement that it is not feedback if the message gives no opportunity to improve. He also mentions getting criticism on some parts of his work can create confusion on the full assignment, since it can make him unsure about parts without the explicit feedback. A third student doesn’t mind getting criticized and does not associate it with a negative feeling.

3.3.2 *“Feedback literate students are proactive in eliciting suggestions from peers or teachers and continuing dialogue with them as needed.”*

All students see opportunities to actively engage with teachers after an on-campus lecture. The students also mention they can ask for feedback on exams after the grades are published. All students agree that it is also possible to obtain feedback from a teacher during lab sessions, but that it is up to the student to ask for it.

During an online activity, they are reluctant to ask questions because they have the feeling of “disturbing” a teacher. If a teacher is on campus, they assume that he/she is there for lectures and is therefore automatically available to answer questions. Some students do not mind asking feedback to a teacher by e-mail since they see it as the best source of information. Other students hesitate because teachers often mention they are busy, and a reminder needs to be sent if there is no reply.

One student mentions a collaborative system as Google Docs as a useful tool while working on a joined task. It allows team members to quickly share feedback on specific parts of a task. The other 3 students are interested in his idea of using such a tool in a similar setting in the future.

All students also refer to occasions where they expected feedback, but did not receive feedback or too late so that it was not possible to properly use it. They did not indicate taking action in asking for this late or missing feedback.

3.3.3 *“Feedback literate students develop habits of striving for continuous improvement on the basis of internal and external feedback.”*

Only one student referred to generating feedback on his own work, while another student mentioned a reflective moment as an opportunity to improve judgement. The students do not further report a systematic drive for continuous improvement.

3.4 Taking action

3.4.1 *“Feedback literate students are aware of the imperative to take action in response to feedback information.”*

Three students feel a sense of obligation to respond to feedback in some way. One of them mentions the effort it took to generate feedback and the moral obligation to take the feedback into account as a token of respect to the feedback giver. A second student feels obligated to use the feedback, but only if he is scoring low, to prevent

the teacher from thinking he is unwilling. If he passed a task and is satisfied with the grade he obtained, he does not feel a necessity to even collect any form of feedback. The third student suggests that he feels obligated to make a decision based on the feedback, but that deciding not to take the feedback into account is also a valid outcome. All students agree on this reasoning.

3.4.2 “Feedback literate students draw inferences from a range of feedback experiences for the purpose of continuous improvement.”

The students see feedback as an opportunity for continuous improvement, but are not giving specific examples during the focus group discussion. Only one student refers to small corrections such as missing graph titles that are easy to change, remember and re-apply. If it is not something that is remembered, it is not deliberately reapplied in a subsequent task or it is not mentioned during the focus group discussion.

3.4.3 “Feedback literate students develop a repertoire of strategies for acting on feedback.”

None of the students mentioned specific strategies, except for writing things down to make sure information is not lost when studying the same topic again.

4 DISCUSSION

4.1 Appreciating feedback

All students see continuous improvement as an important goal of feedback processes, similar to the findings of Dawson et al. [3]. In their study, 90% of students indicated that feedback is about improvement. All our students agree that feedback makes it possible to perform on a higher level for a subsequent task and mentioned occasions with feedback being too late as barriers to properly use it.

Students prefer oral and individual feedback because it gives them the opportunity to start a dialogue and provides a better opportunity to clearly understand the message. The work of Dawson et al. [3] confirms that face-to-face interactions are students' most favoured medium to facilitate effective feedback. For the same reason, the students do not see a chat session as a valuable alternative, as the message may still be open to interpretation. Winstone et al. [9] reports students' particular frustration about teachers' use of complicated language, but none of our students explicitly mentions this. Their preference for oral and individual feedback may also be related to the lack of clarity of the required standards.

All students state that they only write down their feedback on paper, or just try to remember it. This makes it more difficult to revisit feedback and to transfer what they have learned from earlier feedback experiences. By asking students to reflect on feedback at specific times during the semester and by storing these reports in a student-centred portfolio, students are given the opportunity to easily revisit previous feedback experiences and conclusions at any point in their study. Since feedback literate students seem to welcome technology-enabled approaches to store, access and revisit feedback [5], such digital reflective reports can also be an opportunity to nurture self-regulatory learning behaviours and make students more aware of their current feedback opportunities [7].

4.2 Making judgments

When they are not cooperating as a team, students indicate that they do not rely on the competence of their peers to give feedback and see teacher feedback as the only valid input. The work of McConlogue [10] also shows a distrust of peers' ability to judge and argues that becoming a peer assessor is a long-term process where initial peer feedback should be withheld until students develop expertise in composing feedback. Contributing to peer feedback will help students to better self-evaluate their work by making comparisons with the work of others [10]. Since teachers' resources are limited, it is also important for feedback literature students to see peer feedback as a process that augments teacher feedback [2], [11]. Therefore, when introducing a peer feedback system, it will be essential to use a clear framework and to explain students how they should be assessing work and composing comments.

Students also indicate the difficulty of judging open exercises. They indicate their preference towards formative oral feedback to get confirmation that they are on the right track or to receive hints how to get on the right track. Having the opportunity to start a dialogue with a teacher makes it is easier to find out what the exact expectations are and how they can be met.

One student mentioned 'a moment of reflection' as a synonym for feedback. He indicated it improves the judgement of his own work, which is an important aspect of feedback literate students [5]. As stated earlier, the introduction of reflection reports can help students in developing these self-evaluating capacities over time.

4.3 Managing affect

During the discussion, students indicate that they are proactive by asking questions during on-campus activities and know that this is their own responsibility. During online activities they are reluctant to take this active role and to ask questions. However, when they are expecting feedback but do not receive it, they do not contact the teacher. According to Dawson et al. [3] timeliness to use feedback in subsequent work is a fundamental requirement for feedback to occur at all. Since our students explicitly mention timeliness and improvement of subsequent work as important, but not mention their own role in it, it appears they consider the timely provision of feedback and the opportunity to use it in their later work as a sole responsibility of the teaching staff. Therefore, they might miss an opportunity to use it in a different course or setting. While it is understandable to first-year students to be hesitant to contact a teacher, it can also be an opportunity to start a dialogue. Teachers must make students aware that they are always free to ask for feedback, especially if they are expecting it.

During the discussion, students did not express emotional discomfort towards receiving critical feedback. One student explicitly mentioned he does not mind getting criticized and does not even associate it with a negative feeling. However, they did state that critical feedback should always be accompanied by an opportunity to improve.

4.4 Taking action

When students receive feedback, most of them initially claim to feel a sense of obligation to respond to it in some way. When one student claims that deciding not to take feedback into account is also an action and a valid outcome, the other students agree on this reasoning. This conclusion may indicate that students in general now the purpose of feedback, but that they are not always sure how to use it if the feedback message does not clearly formulate an instruction on how to improve. Bearman et al. confirms that feedback might simply be ignored if students do not understand what to do differently [12]. Since Winstone et al. [9] indicates it is the responsibility of educators to challenge the students expectations on feedback by encouraging practices that promote self-regulation rather than dependence on explicit instruction, it is important for educators to give students the possibility to see how their feedback can be used in subsequent work.

5 CONCLUSIONS AND FURTHER DEVELOPMENTS

All students show their appreciation towards feedback and see continuous improvement as an important goal of feedback processes. They prefer a dialogue to avoid misinterpretation of the feedback message, so it is important that they have opportunities for these face-to-face discussions. Teachers also have to make students aware that they can ask for feedback when they expect it but do not receive it. Additionally, teachers should give students the possibility to take action by showing how feedback can be used in other work to prevent students from ignoring it.

To promote student feedback literacy in the future, it is important that students see peer feedback as an additional source of information, as they currently see teacher feedback as the only valid input. To build thrust in their peers' ability to judge, guiding students in assessing work and composing comments to peers will be essential. Additionally, contributing to peer feedback will help students to better self-evaluate their own work.

With the continuing focus to promote student feedback literacy, we will also introduce digital reflective reports at specific times during the semester. By capturing these reports in a student-centred portfolio, students will learn to work with feedback in a structured way and will have the opportunity to revisit previous experiences and conclusions at any point in their study.

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